

Research Article

Financial Services: A Case study of Street Vendors issues with reference to Gudiwada Town, Andhra Pradesh

P.Murali

Lecturer In Commerce TSR&ERR GDC Pamarru Krishna Dt.

Corresponding Author: P.Murali

Abstract

Financial services includes services of banking, insurance and risk management sectors and individual and corporate finance. Financial services provides finance which is used by the people to purchase goods on hire purchase. In the process of rendering financial services by the various financial institutes they earn the profit. A street vendor is a person who moves from one place to another place for selling of products in the streets of the towns and villages. They are categorised depending on their sale of goods or place of their business. Peddlers are those street vendors who sales goods by having a temporary selling public places in the streets. Majority of the street vendors are earning very low income per month. Even though street vendors are not getting enough credit facility from banks, but about 82 percentage of street vendors have their personal bank account. Most of the street vendors does not know about the benefits and security from the insurance it is evident with 82 percent of street vendors does not have insurance policy.

Keywords: Development of Economy, Financial services, street vendor, Insurance

Introduction

Economic development is very vital for any nation as it is one of the tool by which the nation's development is evaluated. Development of economy is not possible with the development of a particular sector in economy; it is possible only with the all-round development of the economy. Economic prosperity of people in any country is caused by the economic growth of that nation and this economic prosperity is nothing but people higher standard of living. Economic development is also indicated by availability of financial services in a country .More availability of financial services in a country is more economically developed country. Financial services includes services of banking, insurance and risk management sectors and individual and corporate finance. Financial services provides finance which is used by the people to purchase goods on hire purchase. In the process of rendering financial services by the various financial institutes they earn the profit. These financial institutions promotes investment, production and saving etc. A street vendor is a person who moves from one place to another place for selling of products in the streets of the towns and villages. They are categorised depending on their sale of goods or place of their business. Peddlers are those street vendors who sales goods by having a temporary selling public places in the streets. The unemployment and poverty forces the people to become the street vendors in search of

employment and better life. Being part of lower section of the society they do not have access to education or skill to work in formal sector therefore they continue in unorganised economy without having any job guarantee and with perpetual uncertainty. 49.48 lakhs street vendors are identified in India and the Uttarpradesh state has the highest number of street vendors approximately 8.49 lakhs.

Objectives and Research Methodology

To know the socio-economic conditions of street hawkers in Gudiwada town area and to understand the usage of financial services by street vendors of Gudiwada city region in Andhrapradesh. The Gudiwada town spread over an area of 12.67 km² (4.89 sq mi) with 36 election wards and Gudiwada is politically and geographically very significant area to carry out the research study. The questionnaire was prepared and designed on the basis of previous literature and a survey was conducted for a period of ten days and convenient sampling method was applied to select sample for the study. The sample consist of a total of 40 samples and secondary data was collected from the research articles, google, Wikipedia, etc., simple percentage method was analyzed to interpret the data.

Review of Literature

Ajay Gautham, BS Waghmare (2021) "The plight of street vendors the failure of governance and development" In this paper the authors attempted explore and expose the vulnerability, fragility, and marginalization of this section under faulty urban governance and development practices by tracking their lives, pains, and plight as vendors." Dr. A.PRIYA, MEENACHI.T, (2022): "A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACED BY STREET VENDORS WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICTS" The authors tried in this research article paper that the problems faced by the street vendors and concluded that street vendors are facing many issues like health condition, climate change and ignorance about government schemes and policies that are implemented for the benefit of them."

Sharit Bhowmik (2005), in this study "Street Vendors in Asia: A Review" analyzed that the street vendors in Asian countries namely Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Bangkok (Thailand), Singapore, Kuala Lumpur, Manila, Hanoi, Cambodia, Seoul and India. The study examined the magnitude of street vending in different countries. The assessment found that the number of street vendors in the countries was on an increase.

Chakraborty, Samarpita Koley: "Socio-Economic View on Street Vendors: A Study of a Daily Market at Jamshedpur Parikshit Chakraborty, Samarpita Koley" In this paper the authors concluded that the male street hawker's income is better than the women street vendors and the pattern of subsistence at market place not up to the standard.

Nidan (2010): in his paper "Study on Street Vendors at Patna (Bihar)" It was analyzed that most of the respondents chose vending as a profession because there were no other jobs available, entry was easier and investment was low. In also described the problems faced by female street vendors and revealed that lack of protection and lack of basic facilities such as toilets and crèches for their children were the major constraints faced by them.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Showing the Gender of the respondents

Gender	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Male	27	68
Female	13	32
Total	40	100

Interpretation: The above table and pie chart explains that out of cent, 68 percentages are male street vendors and only 32 percent of women are participating in the activities of the street vending process.

Table 2: Showing the Age of the respondents

Age	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Below 30	15	38
31 to 40	11	28
41 to 50	09	22
51 to 60	5	12
Total	40	100

Interpretation: The above both table and graph describes that the highest participants in the street vendor activities are below 30 years of age and the lowest participants are above the age of 50 years.

Table 3: Showing the Income Levels of the respondents

Income per Month	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Below Rs.5,000	16	40
Rs.5,001-10,000	12	30
Rs.10,001-15,000	9	23
Above Rs.15,000	3	07
Total	40	100

Interpretation: From the above table and chart it is clarify that about 40 percent of respondents are earning very low income per month it means that majority of the respondents are earning very low income and 7 percent of the respondents only earning above Rs. 15,000 /- per month it shows that how hard to earn the money in this economic activity.

Table 4: Showing the bank account holder of the respondents

Having BankAccount	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	33	83
No	07	17
Total	40	100

Interpretation: The above both table and diagram clarifies that about 83 percentage of street vendors are having bank accounts their own . This positive indicator is achieved with the scheme like Pradhanamatri Jandhan Yojana (PMJY).

Table 5:Showing the Sources of Credit of the respondents

Source of Credit	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Own	09	22
Friends & Relatives	16	40
Money Lenders	13	33
Others	02	05
Total	40	100

Interpretation: The above table and graphs simplifies that majority of the street vendors are still depending on money lenders and friends and relatives for their daily business credit necessities

Table 6:Showing Investment in the bank (FD) of the respondents

Invested in Bank	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	19	47
No	21	53
Total	40	100

Interpretation: It is clear up from the above table and pie chart that 47 percent of street vendors have investment in the bank through fixed deposits it mean though they are not getting the credit facility from the banks required by them, they are making investment in banks at reasonable level.

Table7:Showing Having Insurance facility of the respondents

Insurance having	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	07	18
No	33	82
Total	40	100

Interpretation: Insurance service is also one of the service in the financial services. The 82 percent of street vendors does not have insurance facility. It implies that how much street vendors to be educated regarding the insurance and its benefits in the form of risk coverage etc.

Findings:

1. The men street vendors are dominating the street vendor business activity comparing with women street vendors with 68 percent which is more than double of women participation percentage (32 percent)
2. Majority of the street vendors are earning very low income per month.
3. Even though street vendors are not getting enough credit facility from banks, but about 82 percentage of street vendors have their personal bank account.
4. Most of the street vendors does not know about the benefits and security from the insurance it is evident with 82 percent of street vendors does not have insurance policy

Conclusion: Street vendors are to be encouraged by the financial institutes by providing them with proper financial services like proving and making availability of credit at reasonable and affordable rate of interest. Street vendors are part of the society and they provide goods at door step at lower prices and at convenient time.

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